

EFFECTIVE WAYS OF TEACHING RUSSIAN TO YOUNG LEARNERS THROUGH TALES, TOYS AND SONGS

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Abstract: The goal of this paper is to demonstrate that, when used appropriately and with clearly defined goals, songs and games can be an amazing tool for language teachers.

Keywords: Songs, games, young learners, teaching vocabulary

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

Games are popular with people of all ages and can encourage children to learn while also reducing classroom stress. The majority of young learners consider singing to be a fun activity. The fact that students frequently learn without realizing it is one of the many benefits of using songs as a teaching tool. Learning a new language never comes easy. Adults are able to make their own decisions regarding whether or not to begin the lengthy process of learning a new language. In contrast, children do not have a choice. They begin learning a foreign language at a young age. As I began my career in education, I had the opportunity to meet a wide range of students: gifted, hardworking individuals as well as lazy bones My methodology teachers taught me that teaching a foreign language is not like cooking. We should make an effort to learn about our students' abilities and find the best ways to assist them in the long and difficult process of learning a new language. I learned early on that a child is just a child: They all have an inherent curiosity and playful disposition. As a result, why shouldn't I, as a teacher, utilize these characteristics to enhance learning? If I look at my Russian classes from the perspective of a child, there should be laughter and fun in them, and children should let go of their inhibitions because they can learn in a comfortable and encouraging environment. This paper aims to demonstrate that, when used appropriately and with clearly defined goals, songs and games can be useful tools for language teachers. Games are popular with people of all ages, can inspire children to learn, and they can even take the stress out of classrooms. The majority of young learners find singing to be a fun activity. The fact that students frequently learn without realizing it is one of the many benefits of using songs as a teaching tool. They sing the songs at home and even teach them to their parents, siblings, or other loved ones. Knowing the

characteristics of the age group we teach is essential. That makes it easier for us to comprehend their behavior and the operation of their tiny brains. If we have a thorough understanding of their capabilities and requirements, we will only be successful. Who are the adolescent students?

Teachers may find teaching children to be an exciting adventure. I can't think of a more difficult age group that would require so much ingenuity, patience, and creativity. I learned over the course of my years working with them that if I wanted my teaching to succeed, I had to become like those young children. Naturally, not in behavior, but in spirit. Understanding who they are and how they "work," or the way they think, act, and behave, as well as the way their tiny brains function and absorb new information, will help us pique their interest in learning a foreign language at such a young age. When we choose what and how to teach, the age of the students plays a big role. Age-related differences in needs, abilities, and cognitive abilities are common. Young children learn a lot of a foreign language through play, while adults use more abstract thinking. The generalizations made for young learners may require more in-depth analysis and some subcategorization because children differ greatly by one year. The following grouping reflects the EFL teaching environment and the Russian learners in primary education in Romania, despite the fact that various sources classify young learners based on age or grade level:

Very young students whose ages: ages three to six; grade: Education for children in preschool 7- to 10-year-olds; grade: Age range: kindergarten through fourth grade 11- to 12-year-olds; grade: 5th through 6th grade Young children learn in different ways than older children, adolescents, and adults do:

Their understanding comes not only from explanations, but also from what they see, hear, and have the chance to touch and interact with After about ten minutes, they may easily become disinterested and bored if the activities are not particularly engaging.

Young children are more open to learning a new language and have a positive attitude about it. Teaching Vocabulary to Young Students With young students, learning vocabulary is relatively simple because the words they need are concrete—things they can see, touch, taste, play with, etc. so that the meaning of the words can be easily understood without the need for complicated explanations or translations. How better to teach the word "apple" to children than to show them an apple or a picture of one, or to teach them some basic words for emotions like "happy," "angry," and so on? by squinting? They really like it, and they tend to remember the words better this way than when they hear the translation in their native language. Naturally, this is the case because involving a variety of skills helps the learning process. The sooner students can express themselves in Russian,

The more motivated they will be, the more important it is to provide them with a vocabulary bank to draw from, starting with nouns and adjectives. While auditory learners are in their element listening, kinaesthetic and tactile learners will latch on to using their bodies to respond to the music. Visual learners can look at story pictures or vocabulary flashcards related to the song. They can also see other people performing the actions. Except for a small number of people who don't like music, everyone is happy!

Songs are fun and encourage students to learn Russian. One of the biggest advantages is that using music in the classroom can improve the mood, give students a boost of energy, and give them a sense of purpose that keeps them interested and motivated to learn Russian. Songs can help build confidence. Using songs to teach Russian is a great way for kids to listen to and practice their Russian in a group setting. They can join in when they can without being picked on, and they learn more with each listening. Children who are shy or have trouble learning are encouraged to sing or speak in choir, which gives them the confidence to speak a foreign language. This can significantly boost confidence, which carries over to all learning.

Songs help us remember things. We can remember lines from a variety of songs and keep repeating them: This is precisely what we want for our students of Russian.

Songs aid in classroom management. The simple fact that playing a song immediately piques the interest of the class is absolutely essential for a teacher. Every student takes part in the movements, sounds, and/or songs. If not already, the teacher now has their attention! Students can also "get rid of" extra energy by listening to songs, especially action songs, which can help them relax and get ready to start their work. As a concluding sentence for anyone who is new to using songs and may wonder, "Why songs?" There are many reasons songs are great. The melodies make it easier for children to remember the words. The songs' rhythm aids the children in speaking naturally. Put simply, they are excellent practice! Additionally, many current songs for Russian as a Second Language (ESL) and Russian as a Foreign Language (EFL) incorporate activities and games. We can therefore perform the action while singing "This is the way I wash my face." The child's memory is really helped by this combination of singing and acting. Also, it's fun! The significance and function of games in language acquisition. Language acquisition is challenging. Every moment requires effort, which must be sustained over an extended period of time. Many students use games to keep their interest and work going. Learning one's native language is not the same as learning a foreign language. As we get older, we learn our native language, which doesn't seem like a lot of work for a healthy person. We acquire knowledge from our

surroundings, family, and friends. We frequently speak our native tongue. The majority of the time, learning a second language is limited to one or two weekly lessons. Only a small number of students are willing to put in extra effort to improve their Russian or to hear the language in action (by listening to Russian songs, meeting native speakers, or watching unsynchronized movies or cartoons). Teachers can use games to create contexts where students can use and understand the language. The students want to participate, but they need to understand what others are saying or writing in order to do so. They also need to speak or write in order to express their own viewpoint or provide information. One approach to assisting students in experiencing language rather than merely studying it is through games. 2) The requirement for meaningfulness in language learning has been recognized for some time (Wright, Betteridge, and Buckby, 2006, page 2). The fact that students respond to the material in a specific way is a useful interpretation of "meaningfulness." The content clearly has meaning for them if they are amused, enraged, intrigued, or surprised. As a result, they will have a better chance of remembering the meaning of the language they hear, read, write, and speak. Games must be considered an essential part of a teacher's arsenal if it is acknowledged that they can provide meaningful and intense language practice. Therefore, they should not only be used on wet days and at the end of the term! If we were to use a scientific term to describe games, we would say that they are a variety of activities that create a pleasant and captivating atmosphere for participants. According to Boudains and Boudains, games are defined as Games are activities that students engage in for the sole purpose of having fun, being curious, or engaging in competitive endeavors (Boudains&Boudains, 1990, p. In order to maintain the boundaries of fair play and accomplish the intended objective, games essentially require that all players adhere to a specific set of rules. According to Lewis and Bedson, the game's rules clearly limit the children's ability to make decisions on their own.

Four characteristics of games are distinguished by Stevick. The first is that players share something, like the ability to play the game or what they need to play (cards, dice, board, etc.). The game's rules are the second feature. The aspect of this game is that any restrictions placed on the players' actions leave them with enough latitude to make it difficult to predict exactly what they will do. 129 Stevick, 1982). As a result, players are able to respond to their surroundings and select the best strategy for winning the game. The goal of the game is the final feature that Stevick mentions. In order for students to comprehend the game's objectives, the instructor should mention the goal. Teachers choose to incorporate games into their language instruction for a variety of reasons. The use of games in Russian classes has been well documented and widely acknowledged to have a positive effect on the

language learning process of students. They can be used as warm-ups, filler activities, or as the main point of the lesson plan or even the syllabus as a whole.

Games contribute to learners' overall language development. According to McCallum, there are a number of legitimate reasons to use games in the language classroom, not the least of which is the pure enjoyment of a moment of relaxation following arduous drilling. Lewis and Bedson list the following as some of the reasons games should be used: They not only serve as a fun and motivating activity, but they also provide a context in which the language is embedded. Because the game creates its own world, this setting is "authentic." It takes the place of external reality for the entirety of the game. 1999, p. 3) O'Dell and Head contribute to this discussion by stating that students learn words most effectively when they manipulate and personalize them in a memorable way. Games play a particularly significant role in vocabulary acquisition for these two reasons: O'Dell & Head, 2003, p.4), they give students the chance to use words in a memorable context and offer a fun way to revisit words.

As a result, games can indicate innovation and, when used appropriately, foster a friendly atmosphere between educators and students. The fact that students must communicate at some point during games is the most important aspect. It is widely acknowledged that playing makes students more communicative and less afraid of using a foreign language. They enjoy using the language because they feel like they can talk to each other without having to worry about how good their grammar is. According to McCallum, Students are less self-conscious when playing games, so they are more likely to experiment and freely participate in learning a new language. Engaging games can enhance the learning process for both students and teachers. This indicates that language learning occurs subconsciously for students.

When using games, we should consider Allen's (1983) thoughts that games are helpful because they can make students feel like certain words are important and necessary because the game's goal cannot be achieved without them.

One of the most important ways to teach a language class effectively is through games. Children can't get enough of video games. For them, nothing is more fun than playing games, where they feel happy and free. It doesn't matter whether it's indoors or out; The significance of games cannot be denied. You have achieved your objectives if games help students learn, have fun, and feel free. Additionally, games improve language skills; While interacting with one another, students improve their social skills and cultivate positive relationships. Do not limit students to indoor games. When the weather is good, it's good to play games outside. Even though we are aware that board games are best played inside, they

can also be played outside. We can make use of garden seats outside in the playground as desks. The students will be exuberant even at the thought of going out. They have already become dissatisfied with sitting in the same class and at the same desks. They will proceed down the stairs two by two as soon as they hear, "Let's go to the playground, it's game time." Regardless of our objective – speaking, grammatical points, or vocabulary – we must believe that every game our students play is far more beneficial than a plethora of worksheets and exercises, and that it produces more positive outcomes than anything else.

How frequently should games be used? There should not be a set time for games set by teachers. The majority of teachers keep games and songs for Fridays or term-end periods. Having a game that is ready to use in our pocket is always beneficial. We should take our children out and use them when we notice that they are tired and bored. We can reenergize our young ones by getting students to play short games for 10 or 15 minutes. You actually win, so it is not a waste of time. Another point to keep in mind: It will be helpful if we include the games we use for each unit in the annual plan. In most cases, group games are more beneficial. Children become closer to one another as a result of their rivalry. Before a game, they frequently look through their books or notebooks because they feel like they should be first. During a game, we should occasionally mix the groups so that they can play with different ones. However, we need to exercise caution regarding the intensity of the rivalry because, if the feeling is too strong, it may initiate World War III. Young students enjoy engaging games and are vivacious and active. Rewarding is one important aspect of using games to teach Russian. This point should not be overlooked. Everyone who accomplishes a difficult task successfully would appreciate some recognition or a present. Our students receive constant praise. But motivating them is giving them small gifts. They do not necessarily have to be costly. We can give our students different gifts based on their ages. A simple pen, a sticker, or a pencil will suffice for young learners. Even little things can make them happy. Give the winners a pretty, colorful bag filled with small chocolates, candies, and other treats.

Teachers lament that they do not have sufficient time to prepare the games. Certain games definitely require preparation and time. If a game requires some stationery, like paste crayons, cardboard, etc., It takes a long time. However, there are some straightforward games that do not necessitate any prior preparation. You won't have to look for game instructions when you need them if you have an archive with them in your personal file. It can be helpful to use durable materials to make certain materials for various games so that they won't break easily and can be used multiple times. You can laminate flashcards; We don't have to prepare the materials for the same game or song repeatedly because we can use cardstock

instead of regular paper. Classroom Russian instruction that works well is through the use of games. You will achieve the best classroom results in this manner. Students are motivated by it. Young learners learn positive social attitudes and prepare for life through games. Games teach cooperation, sharing, and helping one another. A child learns through doing, living, trying, and copying other people. As a result, this kind of learning lasts. Some emotions, like the desire to lose and the satisfaction of winning, may surface during games. This gives the teacher an idea of the character of the student. Therefore, games are essential activities for dedicated educators. Final Thoughts: In primary schools, teaching Russian as a Foreign Language relies heavily on songs and games. At any point in the lesson, games can be used. They are used for more than just having fun in the classroom; they also have educational purposes. They are a way to learn new vocabulary and a never-ending source of vocabulary improvement. Songs combine entertainment, activity, motivation, and important didactic claims. The children learn about the culture of the other country and get to know the British children's favorite songs, rhymes, and games. There are a wide variety of songs and games for Russian teachers to choose from, each with its own unique features and actions. We should always keep in mind the lesson's goal and select games or songs that help us accomplish it. Music or games aren't just for passing the time; They must be used with care. When teachers also enjoy singing and playing with their students in class, we get the best results because we can have a positive impact on the children's development, get to know them better, and meet and satisfy their needs.

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